

Supporting Information - **Molecular dynamics insights into structural and hydration dynamics of LAT1 bound to ligands and JPH203-induced inward-open arrest**

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Figure S1. Starting frames of each simulation system. Starting frames of the cpd1 (A), cpd5 (B), and cpd12 (C) simulations aligned to the PDB structure 7DSQ, with the co-crystallized ligand (diiodotyrosine) shown in green. (D) Starting frame of JPH simulation aligned to its structure bound to 8XPU.

Figure S2. Protein and ligand RMSD. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) for protein's backbone (blue) and ligand heavy atoms (red line). Each simulation system consists of five independent replicates, which are separated by vertical lines. The first frame of each replicate (identical across all five replicates) was used as the reference structure.

Figure S3. Representation of dihedral angle evolution of ligands responsible for ligand's RMSD change in spiking frames. Torsion angle evolution of cpd1 (A), cpd5 (B), cpd12 (C), and JPH (D). Representative spiking frames are shown for cpd1, rep 2 (8555 ns) (E); cpd5, rep 1 (6250 ns) (F); cpd12, rep 5 (27500 ns) (G); and JPH, rep 2 (upward rotation, 7250 ns) and rep 4 (downward rotation, 22500ns) (H). The ligand in the starting frame is shown in grey.

Table S1. Trajectory clustering based on heavy atom RMSD of ligands (cut-off: 1 Å of ligand's heavy atoms). The RMSD comparing the cluster representative with the initial docking pose are available for each cluster (Cluster 1-5: C1-C5). Underlined clusters represent highest ligand RMSD change.

	Cpd1		Cpd5		Cpd12		JPH	
	Freq. %	RMSD	Freq. %	RMSD	Freq. %	RMSD	Freq. %	RMSD
C1	74	0.34	18	1.63	31	1.11	54	1.39
C2	12	0.62	11	1.5	21	1.87	13	1.37
C3	<u>7</u>	<u>1.2</u>	<u>9</u>	<u>2.36</u>	<u>11</u>	<u>2.24</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>2.82</u>
C4	4	1.07	5.7	2.06	10.3	2.66	7	1.97
C5	0.9	1.15	5.3	1.63	3.71	2.19	4	2.39

Table S2. Protein ligand interaction frequency. Cumulative frequency protein-ligand interactions/contacts along the full analyzed trajectory. Main interaction types (int) are coded as WB: water-bridge, HF: hydrophobic and HB: hydrogen bond.

Cpd	Y289	Y248	Y259	S338	F400	N404	W405	E136	S144	K204
Int	WB	HF, WB	HB,WB,HF	HB,WB	HF	HB,WB	HF	HB,WB	HB,WB	Ionic, HB
Cpd1	58	6	47	27	28	38	63	9	1	1
Cpd5	18	10	24	43	35	38	66	8	16	25
Cpd12	3	29	43	42	42	27	24	1	33	47
JPH	47	0	21	37	52	19	5	18	9	2

Figure S4. Cluster representatives based on ligand's RMSD. Clusters 1 and 3 of cpd1 (**A, B**) and cpd12 (**C, D**). ending frames of cpd12 in rep 3 (**E**), clusters 1 and 3 of cpd5 (**F, G**), representative snapshot obtained from rep 2 of cpd5 (**H**) and clusters 1, 3, and 5 of JPH (**I-K**). Of note, cpd5 was stably accommodated between H6–H3–H10 in rep 2 (12600ns), forming a persistent cation– π interaction with K132 (H3) (**H**). In cpd12, the naphthalene moiety remained within the H6/10 subpocket, while the amino acid head group shifted toward cavity B resulting in a transverse pose in rep 2 and rep 3. In rep 3 (18800ns), cpd12 established a stable hydrogen-bond interactions with K204 and S338, followed by interaction with Y259 that lead to the side-chain rotation of Y259 and remained stable once formed (**E**).

Table S3. Principal component analyses. Contributions of PC1 and PC2 for the overall system variance (in %) for each system.

System	PC1	H1/H6/H7	H11/H12	H4/H9	Upper H1/H6	Upper H2/H7	Lower H5	Upper H10	H3/H8
Apo	46	Yes	Yes	Yes					Yes
Cpd1	46	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes
Cpd5	36	Yes	Yes	Yes			Inverted		Yes
Cpd12	28	Inverted	Yes				Yes		Yes

JPH	45	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
System	PC2	H1/H6/H7	H11/H12	H4/H9	Upper H1/H6	Upper H2/H7	Lower H5	Upper H10	H3/H8
Apo	15.5								
Cpd1	22.8	Yes					Yes		Yes
Cpd5	21.3	Yes							
Cpd12	21.9		Yes		Yes				
JPH	23.4		Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes

Figure S5. PC1 extreme motions and PCA scatter plots. Extreme conformations along PC1 were extracted and visualized in PyMOL to depict the dominant structural rearrangements. First principal component (PC1) motions for the cpd5, cpd12, and JPH systems (**A**) and PCA scatter plots of all systems (**B**). Color shading represents the density of conformations in PC1–PC2 space, with darker regions indicating higher sampling probability. The merged_system scatter plot was generated from the concatenated trajectory of all systems and represents their projection into a shared conformational space.

Figure S6. Extracellular distance measurement. The distance between C-alpha of I147 (H3) and residues of the bundle domain helices, Y289 (H7), A85 (H2), F252 (H6), and G55 (H1) throughout the simulation is shown. Cpd1, Cpd5, Cpd12, JPH and Apo simulation distances are shown in purple, orange, red, blue and grey colour, respectively. Black dashed line represents the outward open conformation, while red dashed line represents the inward open experimentally derived conformation. Replicates are divided by vertical lines.

Figure S7. Intracellular, mid-section, and H6/10 sub-pocket distance measurements. (A) The distance between R348 (H8) and G55 (H1), F262 (H6), and L274 (H7) of the intracellular region of the bundle domain. (B) mid-section, F400 (H10)-S338 (H8) distances describing the expansion or contraction of the transporter. (C) distance between Y248 (H6) and S401 (H10) lining the H6/H10 sub-pocket. Colour codes are the same as Figure S6 and replicates are divided by vertical lines.

Figure S8. Relevant distances of H11-H12 from transport path for cpd1 (A) and JPH (B). Distance-over-time analysis between residues of H11 (S450), H12 (E457), H3 (I147), H6 (Y248) and H10 (S401), specifically for cpd1 and JPH. Red and black dashed line represent corresponding distances in the inward-open and outward-open conformations, respectively. Replicates are divided by vertical lines.

Summary on helical rearrangement

Our findings indicate that LAT1 undergoes a two-step conformational transition characterized by expansion and contraction of its mid-section (H8–H10). Expansion enables water influx from the extracellular H6/H10 sub-pocket to the transporter's base near IH1, assisting in ligand reorientation, while contraction propels the ligand toward H8 and directs water flow toward the intracellular region. Our results also reveal that the benzoxazole tail of JPH rotates downward during the expansion phase, displacing unfavorable water molecules and stabilizing LAT1 in its inward-open conformation. This mechanism extends beyond the recently reported inhibitory mechanism from cryo-EM structures, which showed JPH blocking the outward-facing conformation^{1,2}.

We further demonstrated how larger substrates, whose tails occupy the H6/H10 sub-pocket, can influence LAT1's residue–residue interactions, triggering coordinated helical movements and water flow. Cpd1—showing the best uptake profile and selectivity—was able to flip properly between H10 and H3 that expanded the mid-section, induced rotation of Y248 toward H11, and promoted the approach of H6 and H10. This motion facilitated water flow from the sub-pocket to the base of the transporter, preparing LAT1 for the subsequent contraction step driven by H10 rotation toward the central binding cavity. Cpd5, despite exhibiting sufficient tail flexibility to leave the H6/H10 sub-pocket toward the deeper H10-H3 region, failed as a whole – including its amino acid head group- to flip properly to expand the mid-section and trigger extracellular closure in this study. In contrast, the rigid naphthalene tail of Cpd12 remained firmly anchored within the H6/H10 sub-pocket. However, a shift of its amino acid head group led to intracellular opening and allowed water flow between cavities A and B. Since leaving the H6/H10 sub-pocket is a prerequisite for conformational change, retention of the naphthalene moiety in this region provides molecular-level insight into the mechanism of action of inhibitors with large hydrophobic side chains, which had previously been proposed to prevent H10 rotation³.

Inner residue-residue interaction analysis in specific replicas

We observed that the side chain of **Y103** (lower H2) faces the cavity, forming hydrogen bonds with D116 (IH1) and N261 (H6), as well as a hydrophobic contact with W257 (H6, see **Table S5**). Interaction of Y103 with JPH in replicate 4 reduces its contacts with D116 and N261 by ~50%. Conversely, when Cpd1 occupies the deeper region of cavity A in rep 3, a new interaction forms between Y103 and Y119 near D116, indicating that these regions move closer together.

The residue **S96**, located in the mid-section of H2, forms an H-bond with W257 in the recognition site of H6 in the apo simulation (>50% of the simulation time, **Table S6**). Except for cpd12, this interaction is largely lost upon ligand binding and is mostly replaced by water bridges in other simulations. The loss of an H-bond may result from W257 participating in π -mediated interactions with the ligand. Notably, both interactions were absent in rep 3 of cpd1 and rep 4 of JPH, where the transporter adopts the inward-open conformation. In contrast, the loss of this interaction in rep 4 of cpd12 is due to a shift of its naphthalene moiety toward H2, increasing the S96–W257 distance from 8 to 12 Å.

N404 (H10) is highly involved in interactions with the compounds' tail, both when accommodated in H6/H10 sub-pocket or in deeper cavity A, between H3 and H10. Monitoring its interaction (**Table S7**) showed its high participation in the water bridge (WB) with E136 and K132 (H3) and D116 (IH1). However, these WBs were totally absent when protein adopted the IO conformation in rep 3 of cpd1. Interestingly, a direct H-bond between N404 and K132 was noticed in very stable replicas (rep 2 of cpd5 and rep 5 of apo simulation), in which the intracellular region was closed noticeably. This raises the idea that

approaching these two residues might have a stabilizing effect on closing the intracellular region.

Lastly, **R348**'s polar contacts (H8, **Table S8**) with residues in the lower region of H6, namely F262, Q265 and E266, are diminished or lost in replicas where the intracellular region undergoes substantial opening and H6 shifts toward surrounding (e.g., rep 3 and rep 4 of cpd1 and JPH, respectively, or rep 1 of ligand free simulation). Indicating that these hydrophilic contacts contribute to stabilizing closure of the intracellular region.

Table S4. Frequencies of internal protein-protein interactions and contacts separated by replicas for Y248 (res1) with other surrounding residues (res2). Main interaction type is coded as HB for Hbonds, WB for water-bridges and HF for hydrophobic.

System	Res1	Res2	rep1	rep2	rep3	rep4	rep5	Main Type
cpd1	Y248	S401	0.85	0.43	0.35	0.54	0.77	HB, WB
	Y248	S450		0.2	0.39	0.73		HB
	Y248	T454		0.2	0.54			HB, WB
cpd5	Y248	S401	0.53		0.69	0.43	0.67	HB
	Y248	S450		0.79	0.2	0.23	0.2	HB
	Y248	T454		0.9	0.21			WB
cpd12	Y248	S401	0.89	0.74	0.59	0.51	0.71	HB, WB
	Y248	S450			0.7	0.62		HB
	Y248	T454				0.48		WB
JPH	Y248	S401	0.34	0.68	0.52	0.65		HB, WB
	Y248	S450	0.38	0.82		0.33	0.56	HB
	Y248	T454	0.33	0.65			0.7	WB
APO	Y248	S401	0.64	0.46	0.53	0.6	0.28	HB
	Y248	S450		0.42	0.28		0.52	HB
	Y248	T454					0.75	WB

Table S5. Frequencies of internal protein-protein interactions and contacts separated by replicas for Y103 (res1) with other surrounding residues (res2). Main interaction type is coded as HB for Hbonds, WB for water-bridges and HF for hydrophobic.

System	Res1	Res2	rep1	rep2	rep3	rep4	rep5	Main Type
cpd1	Y103	D116	0.89	0.95	0.99	0.89	0.91	HB
	Y103	Y119	0.29	0.09	0.9	0.27	0.28	HF
	Y103	W257	0.64	0.31	0.71	0.74	0.8	HF
	Y103	N261	0.93	0.91	0.23	0.1	0.96	HB
cpd5	Y103	D116	0.7	0.93	0.8	0.71	0.86	HB
	Y103	Y119	0.06	0.28	0.04	0.33	0.22	HF
	Y103	W257	0.39	0.83	0.42	0.38	0.27	HF
	Y103	N261	0.8	0.84	0.9	0.12	0.02	HB
cpd12	Y103	D116	0.67	0.78	0.85	0.4	0.88	HB
	Y103	Y119	0.31	0.12	0.11	0.19	0.17	HF
	Y103	W257	0.49	0.31	0.24	0.5	0.45	HF
	Y103	N261	0.29	0.3	0.61		0.91	HB
JPH	Y103	D116	0.98	0.92	0.95	0.55	0.89	HB
	Y103	Y119	0.15	0.13	0.21	0.16	0.19	HF
	Y103	W257	0.28	0.12	0.74	0.29	0.87	HF
	Y103	N261	0.95		0.83	0.55	0.93	HB
Apo	Y103	D116	0.92	0.78	0.91	0.72	0.97	HB
	Y103	Y119	0.12	0.06	0.02	0.14	0.07	HF
	Y103	W257	0.51	0.32	0.54	0.23	0.48	HF
	Y103	N261	0.18	0.72	0.95	0.52	0.78	HB

Table S6. Frequencies of internal protein-protein interactions and contacts separated by replicas for S96 (res1) with other surrounding residues (res2). Main interaction type is coded as HB for Hbonds, WB for water-bridges and HF for hydrophobic.

System	Res1	Res2	rep1	rep2	rep3	rep4	rep5	Main Type
cpd1	S96	W257	0.01	0.19				Hbond
	S96	W257	0.52			0.3	0.85	WB
cpd5	S96	W257	0.33	0.06			0.18	Hbond
	S96	W257	0.08	0.44	0.87	0.11		WB
cpd12	S96	W257	0.63	0.84	0.54		0.48	Hbond
	S96	W257	0.1		0.04		0.11	WB
JPH	S96	W257		0.13		0.08		Hbond
	S96	W257	0.05	0.07	0.78	0.05	0.68	WB
Apo	S96	W257	0.51	0.71	0.98	0.57	0.91	Hbond
	S96	W257	0.12	0.09		0.17	0.06	WB

Table S7. Frequencies of internal protein-protein interactions and contacts separated by replicas for N404 (res1) with other surrounding residues (res2). Main interaction type is coded as HB for Hbonds, WB for water-bridges and HF for hydrophobic.

System	Res1	Res2	rep1	rep2	rep3	rep4	rep5	Main Type
Cpd1	N404	E136	0.73			0.29	0.49	WB
	N404	D116	0.68	0.43		0.29	0.78	WB
	N404	W257			0.99			HB
cpd5	N404	E136		0.47		0.34	0.33	WB
	N404	D116	0.25	0.39			0.24	WB
	N404	K132		0.53				HB
cpd12	N404	E136	0.32					WB
	N404	D116	0.25		0.27		0.26	WB
	N404	Y103		0.34	0.22			WB
	N404	W257		0.52	0.4			WB
	N404	G255			0.39			WB
	N404	N258		0.57	0.49			WB
JPH	N404	E136			0.22		0.53	WB
	N404	D116	0.44		0.8	0.24	0.68	WB
Apo	N404	E136	0.23		0.23	0.37	0.38	WB
	N404	D116	0.51			0.19	0.31	WB
	N404	K132					0.51	HB

Table S8. Frequencies of internal protein-protein interactions and contacts separated by replicas for R348 (res1) with other surrounding residues (res2). Main interaction type is coded as HB for Hbonds, WB for water-bridges and HF for hydrophobic.

System	Res1	Res2	rep1	rep2	rep3	rep4	rep5	Main Type
cpd1	R348	F262					1.11	HB
	R348	E265				0.53		HB, WB
	R348	E266	1.85	2.21	0.84	1.54	1.6	HB, WB, ionic
cpd5	R348	F262	0.44		0.55	0.85		HB, WB, HF
	R348	E265	1.22					HB
	R348	E266	0.47	2.12	1.74	1.86	2.04	HB, WB, ionic
cpd12	R348	F262			0.22	0.39		HB
	R348	E265	0.85	0	0.74	0.26	0.82	HB, WB
	R348	E266	0.65	1.44	0.68	0.42	0	HB, WB, ionic
JPH	R348	F262	0.3	0.81	1.19		0.15	HB, HF
	R348	E265	0.57	0.55	0	0.25		HB, WB
	R348	E266	1.4	1.25	1.47		1.75	HB, WB, ionic
APO	R348	F262		0.33		0.2	0.26	HB, HF
	R348	E265				0.27	0.21	HB, WB
	R348	E266		0.63	0.58	0.41	0.62	HB, WB, ionic

Figure S9. Tilt angle measurements. Residue triplets of helices H1/H6 (A) and H10 (B) of PDB structures. 7DSQ (OO conformation) is shown in grey and 6IRT (IO conformation) in colours. (C) Tilt angles calculated from the C-alpha atoms of residue triplets: F399–S401–I412 and V396–S401–I412 of H10 during simulations. Cpd1, Cpd5, Cpd12, JPH and Apo simulation angles are shown in purple, orange, red, blue and grey colour, respectively. Black dashed line represents the outward open conformation, while red dashed line represents the inward open experimentally derived conformation.

Figure S10. Cavity analysis of cpd1 and cpd5. cavities of cpd1 while its tail is accommodated in the H6/10 subpocket in rep 1 (6000ns) (**A**), during a sudden rotation in rep 2 (12500ns) (**B**), and when this rotation leads to closure of extracellular and opening of intracellular region in rep 3 (16000ns) (**C**). Cpd5 cavities are shown when the ligand rotated toward deeper region of cavity A in cluster 1 (**D**), accommodated in H6/10 subpocket in cluster 2 (**E**) and in rep 2 (12600ns) displaying a binding mode highly similar to that observed in cluster 2 (**F**).

Figure S11. Cavity analysis of cpd12 and JPH. Cavities forming with cpd12 while its amino acid head group is bound to the recognition site in cluster 1 (A), and while it shifts toward cavity B in cluster 3 (B). Cavities formed with cpd12 in rep 2 (12500ns) (C), and rep 3 (18800ns) (D), and during side chain rotation of Y259 in rep 3 (E). Cavities formed with JPH during its tail's downward rotation in rep 4 (F)

Table S9. Cavity analysis by SiteMap for all replicates. Median cavity volumes (\AA^3) are reported for cavity A, cavity B, and the subpocket.

Replicates	Cavity A	Cavity B	Subpocket
cpd1_r1	136,9	172,2	106,7
cpd1_r2	180,1	256,9	107,5
cpd1_r3	64,8	189,3	62,1
cpd1_r4	151,9	206,3	121,3
cpd1_r5	152,5	181,4	107,4
cpd5_r1	141,7	222,3	111,6
cpd5_r2	180,2	211,3	244,6
cpd5_r3	136,5	139,6	103,9
cpd5_r4	139,6	206,8	191,4

cpd5_r5	105,0	186,4	87,8
cpd12_r1	235,5	222,9	218,7
cpd12_r2	175,8	245,6	127,3
cpd12_r3	145,4	241,5	81,6
cpd12_r4	151,3	171,7	127,3
cpd12_r5	132,9	197,9	121,4
JPH_r1	158,3	172,2	177,0
JPH_r2	129,3	270,3	123,5
JPH_r3	194,1	215,6	184,5
JPH_r4	117,3	183,2	86,8
JPH_r5	204,9	250,0	197,9
Apo_r1	144,1	144,1	111,0
Apo_r2	150,9	150,9	123,1
Apo_r3	151,1	151,1	112,2
Apo_r4	146,1	146,1	116,6
Apo_r5	151,8	151,8	114,6

Table S10. Cavity analysis by SiteMap for all clusters. Cavity volumes (\AA^3) are reported for cavity A, cavity B, and the subpocket.

Clusters	Cavity A	Cavity B	Subpocket
cpd1_C1	491	72	69
cpd1_C2	370	70	not reported
cpd1_C3	481	not reported	186
cpd1_C4	524	92	87
cpd1_C5	not reported	103	94
cpd5_C1	584	87	not reported
cpd5_C2	456	76	255
cpd5_C3	297	103	209
cpd5_C4	386	not reported	119
cpd5_C5	464	98	224
cpd12_C1	613	95	211
cpd12_C2	513	97	155
cpd12_C3	not reported	421	126
cpd12_C4	544	327	141
cpd12_C5	not reported	299	not reported
JPH_C1	468	156	80
JPH_C2	431	327	123
JPH_C3	416	215	146
JPH_C4	449	72	131
JPH_C5	158	not reported	not reported

Supplementary note on FEL analysis: Free Energy Landscape (FEL) analysis.

Gibbs free energy landscape analysis was utilized to inspect the energetically favorable conformational states of LAT1. FEL was generated based on the radius of gyration (R_g) and RMSD to understand the protein-ligand interaction dynamics. The radius of gyration (R_g) was calculated using the `gmx gyrate`, which measures the compactness of the protein during the simulation, while RMSD was calculated using the `gmx rms`, representing the deviations of C-alpha atoms during simulation in comparison with the initial conformation. Two-dimensional FEL matrices were derived from R_g -RMSD distributions converted to eps format using the `gmx xpm2ps`. The resulting free landscape analysis represents the relative Gibbs free energies of each conformation in trajectory calculated according to the Boltzmann distributions. Further, to retrieve the representative states, clustering (`gmx cluster`) was performed and cluster centroids associated with lowest energy regions of FEL were selected for further structural analysis. FEL provides insights into the system's stable states, energy barriers, and structural transitions within the given timescale. The R_g and RMSD-based FEL highlights clear differences between the systems (**Figure S12A**). Here, red bins indicate the lowest energy conformations, and blue bins indicate the high energy conformations. Yellow to green regions indicate the metastable states sampled during the simulation. While the ligand-free (apo) simulations displayed a single stable local energy minimum, at low R_g and low RMSD, the simulation of the compound-bound systems show at least one additional conformation. These additional minima (other red regions) remain largely within the same basin indicating the conformational sampling near to the native state. Energy landscape of cpd1's simulations showed two states, one with the minimum of the local energy at the highest R_g and a similar RMSD to the apo form and another with the low R_g and higher RMSD. This indicates that cpd1 binding induces conformational changes that affect the compactness of the system, with these two states appearing interconvertible without any energy barriers. Cpd5 exhibits a similar FEL pattern to the Apo form. However, the local energy minimum is distributed towards the highest RMSD and R_g in contrast to the Apo form. The free energy landscape of cpd12 has shown two distinct basins with the lowest energy minima located in a single basin at the highest RMSD and low R_g when compared with other ligand-bound systems. This displays conformational flexibility and access to less stable states in the second basin. In contrast to these ligand-bound systems, JPH shows fragmented, multiple stable states within the same basin implying conformational flexibility and possible induced fit mechanism to alter the transporter activity.

Further, representative structures were retrieved from the lowest energy minima (*i.e.* red bins where Gibbs free energy is around zero, **Figure S12B**) by clustering, displaying a few conformational changes from the cluster centroid. Among the simulated systems, loss of folding and conformational changes in the H1 are more evident in apo form, cpd12 and JPH's simulations, while cpd1 retains H1-folding/position. In the apo simulations, clusters showed major H10 conformational changes, extending towards the inner membrane of H1 and H6. Indeed, residue F400 closed the channel to exit the kink form (with a movement of distance ~ 4.9 Å) and display distinct open conformations on JPH and cpd1 simulations. We attribute those F400-changes to the positioning of cpd1's hydrophobic tail, between H6 and H10 in one state (cpd1-2) and between H10 and H3 in another state (cpd1-1, **Figure S12C**). Those changes in the cpd1's tail happen concomitantly with the Y248 shift in conformations. Aligning cpd1 clusters with the Apo form revealed that cpd1 bound LAT1 displayed an occluded conformation. For cpd5, the cluster centroids display largely conserved helical conformations, with minimal structural variability across clusters (except F400). This behavior is consistent with the apo-FEL profile despite the variations in ligand flexibility. In contrast, the cpd12 displayed similar ligand conformation and varied helical flexibility (where

kink formation is observed in one of the clusters). This aligns with the two-basin FEL of cpd12 and reflects enhanced conformational plasticity driven primarily by protein rearrangements rather than ligand repositioning. Lastly, JPH relevant clusters (**Figure S12D,E**) reveal a distinct flip upwards of its hydrophobic tail, independently from the H1/H6 region as it happens to cpd1. This supports that cpd1 and JPH have distinct conformational behavior from the other simulated systems, and even when compared with each other.

Figure S12. Free energy landscape analysis. (A) Gibbs free energy landscape of the studied systems. Red bins indicate the lowest energy bins, and green to blue indicate the highest energy bins. (B) corresponding cluster representatives of the lowest energy minima states of each system. (C-E) Relevant clusters from the FEL and the respective ligand orientation within the binding cavity for cpd1 (C) and JPH (D,E).

Figure S13. Cluster representatives of the lowest energy states of cpd5, cpd12 and Apo from the FEL analysis. (A) cpd5 orientation in the binding cavity, (B) cpd12 orientation in the binding cavity and (C) Representative structures of Apo cluster 1 and cluster 2, highlighting the different orientations of H10 and H8.

Figure S14. Distribution of all hydration sites in the OO and IO PDB structures. Visualization of all hydration sites independently from their occupancy values, obtained from WaterMap analysis for the experimentally derived structures: (A) OO-Apo and (B) IO-Apo.

Figure S15. Representation of high occupancy hydration sites (>90% occupancy) of cpd1, cpd5 and cpd12. Representative frames from rep1 (6000ns) and rep3 (16000ns) of cpd1 (A-B), Cluster1 and cluster2 of cpd5 (C-D) and cluster1 and cluster3 of cpd12 (E-F). Colored by their predicted free binding energy from red (high energy and unfavorable) to green (with low energy and favorable to support water molecules).

Table S11. Free energy (ΔG) of hydration sites for the inward open conformation. The values were predicted using WaterMap (see methods), composed by the enthalpic (ΔH) and entropic (ΔS , for 37°C) terms. Occupancy (Occ., 0-1) states for the % of simulated time in which that hydration site was occupied by a water molecule.

IO - apo					IO - with Ligand				
Site	Occ	dH	-@TdS	dG	Site	Occ	dH	-@TdS	dG
1	1	8.02	4.4	12.42	1	0.99	-1.01	4.7	3.69
2	0.99	-0.69	4.7	4.01	2	0.99	-1.74	4.34	2.6
3	0.99	3.4	3.78	7.18	3	0.97	-2.29	4.66	2.37
4	0.89	0.45	3.2	3.65	4	0.96	2.81	3.91	6.72
5	0.89	-0.5	3.1	2.6	5	0.96	-0.91	4.22	3.31
6	0.87	5.24	4.35	9.59	6	0.94	-1.29	3.95	2.66
7	0.8	0.13	2.68	2.81	7	0.89	2.88	3.58	6.46
8	0.78	1.69	2.85	4.54	8	0.89	4.87	4.41	9.28
9	0.69	1.66	2.43	4.09	9	0.87	2.55	3.27	5.82
10	0.69	-1.75	2.29	0.54	10	0.86	-0.07	3.34	3.27
11	0.69	0.65	2.12	2.77	11	0.85	-1.69	3.22	1.53
12	0.68	0.33	2.12	2.45	12	0.81	1.26	3.22	4.48
13	0.68	0.31	1.97	2.28	13	0.8	1.63	3.03	4.66
14	0.68	0.24	2.52	2.76	14	0.73	-1.76	2.74	0.98
15	0.67	-2.07	2.12	0.05	15	0.73	2.53	2.63	5.16
16	0.66	2.16	2.47	4.63	16	0.69	0.84	2.14	2.98
17	0.64	2.06	1.9	3.96	17	0.66	-1.94	2.07	0.13
18	0.63	-0.86	1.97	1.11	18	0.65	0.71	2.34	3.05
19	0.6	1.38	1.77	3.15	19	0.65	-0.9	2.03	1.13
20	0.59	0.46	1.75	2.21	20	0.62	1.63	1.75	3.38
21	0.58	-3.44	2.16	-1.28	21	0.62	1.69	2.27	3.96
22	0.57	2.71	1.65	4.36	22	0.61	1.81	2.15	3.96
23	0.56	3.96	1.86	5.82	23	0.59	0.21	1.92	2.13
24	0.55	1.57	1.73	3.3	24	0.58	1.52	1.76	3.28
25	0.55	1.85	1.69	3.54	25	0.55	-3.27	2.07	-1.2
26	0.55	-0.28	2.09	1.81	26	0.54	-1.45	1.73	0.28
27	0.52	2.04	1.57	3.61	27	0.52	1.99	1.55	3.54
28	0.48	0.7	1.29	1.99	28	0.49	2.46	1.46	3.92
29	0.47	-0.88	1.35	0.47	29	0.48	0.68	1.42	2.1
30	0.46	-0.61	1.42	0.81	30	0.43	1.48	1.32	2.8
31	0.46	2.12	1.34	3.46	31	0.43	3.03	1.48	4.51
32	0.46	4.94	1.82	6.76	32	0.4	0.65	1.09	1.74
33	0.45	0.36	1.32	1.68	33	0.39	4.84	1.22	6.06
34	0.44	-0.29	1.28	0.99	34	0.39	-0.88	1.16	0.28
35	0.42	2.11	1.36	3.47	35	0.38	6.48	1.47	7.95
36	0.42	0.1	1.3	1.4	36	0.38	0.02	1.21	1.23
37	0.4	2.1	1.45	3.55	37	0.37	1.45	1.01	2.46
38	0.39	-0.93	1.03	0.1	38	0.36	2.51	1.02	3.53
39	0.37	-0.76	1.1	0.34	39	0.33	2.91	1.46	4.37
40	0.37	1.08	1.01	2.09	40	0.33	2.83	1.37	4.2
41	0.37	3.33	1.09	4.42	41	0.32	2.56	0.94	3.5
42	0.36	3.24	1.31	4.55	42	0.32	-0.4	0.91	0.51
43	0.36	3.4	1.3	4.7	43	0.3	2.66	1.1	3.76
44	0.36	-0.68	1.15	0.47	44	0.28	0.03	0.86	0.89

45	0.36	-0.81	1.02	0.21
46	0.36	6.17	1.36	7.53
47	0.36	2.43	1.04	3.47
48	0.32	4.9	0.97	5.87
49	0.32	0.48	0.91	1.39
50	0.31	2.69	0.89	3.58
51	0.31	0.89	0.89	1.78
52	0.3	-0.01	0.81	0.8
53	0.29	0.38	0.9	1.28
54	0.29	3.07	0.91	3.98
55	0.29	1.16	0.89	2.05
56	0.29	2.97	1.2	4.17
57	0.28	0.36	0.81	1.17

Table S12. Free energy (ΔG) of hydration sites for the outward open conformation. The values were predicted using WaterMap (see methods), composed by the enthalpic (ΔH) and entropic (ΔS , for 37°C) terms. Occupancy (Occ., 0-1) states for the % of simulated time in which that hydration site was occupied by a water molecule.

OO - apostructure					OO - with Ligand				
Site	Occ	dH	-@TdS	dG	Site	Occ	dH	-@TdS	dG
1	1	3.25	4.15	7.4	1	1	-2.13	5.61	3.48
2	0.99	0.71	4.78	5.49	2	1	6.92	5	11.92
3	0.99	-5.66	4.58	-1.08	3	1	3.49	4.28	7.77
4	0.92	-2.53	3.42	0.89	4	1	1.94	4.52	6.46
5	0.87	0.84	3.18	4.02	5	0.99	1.58	3.91	5.49
6	0.85	-1.89	2.76	0.87	6	0.96	-4.09	4.02	-0.07
7	0.83	3.06	2.88	5.94	7	0.96	5.6	3.24	8.84
8	0.82	2.12	2.93	5.05	8	0.95	-3.12	3.72	0.6
9	0.82	0.31	2.78	3.09	9	0.94	-0.61	3.97	3.36
10	0.82	-2.49	3.21	0.72	10	0.93	6.16	3.27	9.43
11	0.81	-0.13	2.95	2.82	11	0.91	-2.57	3.65	1.08
12	0.75	3.58	3.36	6.94	12	0.87	1.86	3.47	5.33
13	0.72	1.95	2.25	4.2	13	0.84	3.07	2.88	5.95
14	0.72	0.07	2.39	2.46	14	0.82	3.22	3.64	6.86
15	0.71	-0.51	2.62	2.11	15	0.82	-0.54	3.13	2.59
16	0.7	2.44	2.28	4.72	16	0.8	5.06	3.37	8.43
17	0.67	3.81	2.11	5.92	17	0.77	1.08	2.93	4.01
18	0.65	-1.57	2.04	0.47	18	0.71	-2.71	2.79	0.08
19	0.64	-0.15	2.07	1.92	19	0.7	0.4	2.53	2.93
20	0.63	-0.35	1.83	1.48	20	0.68	1.74	2.32	4.06
21	0.61	-3.6	2.07	-1.53	21	0.66	-1.45	2.02	0.57
22	0.59	1.99	2.11	4.1	22	0.65	2.35	2.44	4.79

23	0.56	3.52	1.64	5.16	23	0.65	2.58	2.25	4.83
24	0.54	1.62	1.54	3.16	24	0.65	4.47	2.2	6.67
25	0.52	-0.94	1.79	0.85	25	0.64	-4.23	2.42	-1.81
26	0.52	-0.1	1.66	1.56	26	0.58	0.97	2.14	3.11
27	0.51	2.78	1.58	4.36	27	0.57	2.34	1.71	4.05
28	0.46	3.7	1.36	5.06	28	0.57	1.12	1.69	2.81
29	0.46	0.66	1.27	1.93	29	0.53	-2.39	2.05	-0.34
30	0.46	1.88	1.24	3.12	30	0.52	1.44	1.63	3.07
31	0.44	0.54	1.31	1.85	31	0.5	2.04	2.3	4.34
32	0.43	-0.31	1.25	0.94	32	0.43	-0.23	1.51	1.28
33	0.4	0.25	1.32	1.57	33	0.42	0.31	1.2	1.51
34	0.39	0.11	1.03	1.14	34	0.41	3.11	1.16	4.27
35	0.39	1.91	1.05	2.96	35	0.4	7.45	1.33	8.78
36	0.38	-0.7	1.29	0.59	36	0.4	-0.42	1.1	0.68
37	0.38	-0.64	1.18	0.54	37	0.4	0.24	1.13	1.37
38	0.38	-0.33	1.07	0.74	38	0.39	0.15	1.13	1.28
39	0.37	1.26	1.09	2.35	39	0.38	0	1.18	1.18
40	0.37	1.63	1.66	3.29	40	0.35	-2.16	1.29	-0.87
41	0.36	2.55	0.98	3.53	41	0.35	0.85	0.96	1.81
42	0.36	0.63	0.95	1.58	42	0.34	3.23	0.85	4.08
43	0.36	-0.96	0.96	0	43	0.28	3.83	0.76	4.59
44	0.34	1.04	0.9	1.94	44	0.28	-0.47	0.97	0.5
45	0.34	2.56	0.96	3.52					
46	0.34	-1.27	1.14	-0.13					
47	0.33	-0.39	1.18	0.79					
48	0.33	0.84	0.95	1.79					
49	0.32	5.96	0.94	6.9					
50	0.3	1.29	0.81	2.1					
51	0.3	1.68	0.87	2.55					
52	0.3	2.93	0.88	3.81					
53	0.29	1.21	0.84	2.05					
54	0.29	0.98	0.76	1.74					
55	0.29	0.4	0.94	1.34					
56	0.29	0.2	0.87	1.07					
57	0.28	1.05	0.75	1.8					
58	0.28	1.8	0.78	2.58					

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